

A BRIEF REPORT ABOUT CHARACTERISTICS OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE, ITS HEALTH IMPACTS & AWARENESS OF HOUSEHOLDS ON SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN HYDERABAD CITY

K.Syamala Devi¹, Dr. A.V.V.S. Swamy² and Shaheda Nilofer³

¹*G.Narayanamma Institute of Technology & Science (for Women), Shaikpet, Hyderabad – 104*

²*Department of Environmental Sciences, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur – 510*

³*Lakki Reddy Bal Reddy College of Engineering, Mylavaram, Vijayawada - 230*

ABSTRACT

The Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) Management significantly contributes to the emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and therefore management of this waste is vital for a healthy environment. Management of MSW has become a significant environmental problem especially in metropolitan cities. Pollution and health risks create by improper solid waste management are an important issue that is a cause of major worry to any government, especially in developing countries. Lack of awareness, infrastructure, planning and public awareness is surely the main culprits in this regard. No wonder waste management has become a herculean task for any metropolis.

Technological development, globalization and population growth have accelerated the urbanization in developing countries. Due to sprawling urbanization and uncontrolled growth of population, Municipal Solid Waste Management has become a major problem in India (NEERI; Kumar et al., 2009). Municipal Solid Waste and economic development have a positive correlation in terms of kg / capita / day (Rajput et al., 2009). The composition and characteristics of Municipal Solid Waste vary throughout the world. Even within a country it changes from place to place as it depends on number of factors such as socio economic status, life styles, geographic location, etc (Sharholly et al., 2007; Benitez et al., 2008). Indian cities are now generating 8 times more municipal solid waste than they did in 1947. Presently, about 90 million tons of solid wastes are generated annually as byproducts of industrial, mining, municipal, agricultural and other activities. The per capita generation of MSW increased at a rate of 1 – 1.33% annually (Bhide and Shekdar, 1998; Shekdar, 1999; Pappu et al., 2007). Municipal Solid Waste Management has been a part of public health and sanitation and is entrusted to the municipalities for execution.

Rapid urbanization in the last few decades has led to significant increase in municipal solid waste generation in India. In most cities of India, solid waste management is inefficient as systems adopted are primitive, tools and equipment outdated and inadequate & man power productivity is low. Processing and treatment of waste is limited and final disposal is in unscientific dumpsites, posing problems of soil & water contamination and air pollution. The Hyderabad city has made some efforts in the last few years to improve the municipal solid waste management (MSWM). However, there is still a need to make substantial improvements in the MSWM system of the city and make it in accordance with the Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2016 notified by Ministry of Environment and Forests. These rules lay down procedures for waste collection, segregation, storage, transportation, processing and disposal and further mandated all municipalities and corporations to set up suitable waste treatment and disposal facilities. The present study is aimed at characterizing the solid waste for planning 3R strategy in an effective manner. The public perception, health impacts and the role of rag pickers were also studied for 3 years i.e. 2012-2014.

Key Words: MSW, Globalization, 3Rs Strategy

Introduction:

Municipal Solid Waste as defined by Municipal Solid Waste Rules, 2016 (MOEF, 2016) includes "solid or semi-solid domestic waste, sanitary waste, commercial waste, institutional waste, catering and market waste and other nonresidential wastes, street sweepings, silt removed or collected from the surface drains, horticulture waste, agriculture and dairy waste, treated bio-medical waste excluding industrial waste, bio-medical waste and e-waste, battery waste, radio-active waste generated in the area under the local authorities and other authorities and other entities".

Municipal solid waste (MSW) generally includes degradable (paper, textiles, food waste, straw and yard waste), partially degradable (wood, disposable napkins and sludge) and non-degradable materials (leather, plastics, rubbers, metals, glass, ash from fuel burning like coal, briquettes or woods, dust and electronic waste). Economic and demographic growth of cities, changing life styles of people, changing land use patterns and technological advancements led to increase in quantity and complexity of urban Municipal Solid Waste generation.

The present study is aimed at characterizing the solid waste for planning 3R strategy in an effective manner. The public perception, health impacts and the role of rag pickers were also studied for 3 years i.e. 2012-2014. The present study has been carried out with the following objectives:

1. To study the characteristics of the municipal solid waste at Jawahar Nagar, Gudimalkapur Market, Mehdipatnam Market, Dump near Dilsukh Nagar Bus Depot and Kukatpally Market areas.
2. To study the perceptions of households on the waste handling and disposal in Hyderabad city.
3. To study the socio-economic conditions of rag pickers, at Jawahar nagar dump site.
4. To examine the scope of increasing solid waste management within the scope of MSW (Handling and Disposal) Rules, 2000.
5. To recommend measures to improve efficiency of handling and disposal, public participation and emancipation of rag pickers.

Five stations have been selected as study areas viz. Jawahar Nagar Dump site (Station - I), Gudimalkapur Market (Station - II), Mehdipatnam Market (Station - III), Dilsukh Nagar Bus Depot (Station - IV) and Kukatpally Market (Station - V).

The study included: (1) Characteristics of MSW (2) Study on health impacts of dumpsites (3) Perceptions of households on the management of MSW (4) Socio-economic conditions of Rag Pickers at dump sites.

At these five selected stations, the characteristics of solid waste such as: Density, Moisture, Ash Content, pH, Nitrogen, phosphorus, Potassium, Total Organic Matter, Total Organic Carbon and C/N ratio have been studied. The present study has been carried out from 2012 to 2014 at the five selected stations. The MSW Characteristics were estimated in every alternative months i.e., January, March, May, July, September, November at the rate of six samples per year from each site. The corresponding values of each parameter were expressed in standard units.

The health impacts, household perceptions were studied by administration of questionnaires and 250 rag pickers were interviewed and responses were recorded in questionnaires. One thousand households were given questionnaires and only 450 families have responded. For studying perceptions of households, 800 residents at Dilsukh Nagar and 900 at Kukatpally were served the questionnaires of which 380 and 415 responses were received from Dilsukh Nagar and Kukatpally, respectively. The opinion of public on health impacts and perceptions on solid waste management were analyzed question wise and presented in this thesis.

The responses of public and rag pickers were analyzed and discussed in the light of the objectives of the study and have been used as basis to recommend measures for effective management of solid waste in Hyderabad City.

The physico-chemical parameters of the solid waste are described as follows:

Density:

The lowest density of solid waste at five stations in 2012 was recorded at station – IV with 187 kg/m³ and highest density was at station – I with 376 kg/m³. In the year 2013, the minimum density was recorded at station – IV and maximum was at station – I, similarly in 2014, the minimum and maximum values were at station – IV and station – I, respectively. The lowest density in the entire study period was observed at station – IV was 187 kg/m³ in 2012 and highest was at station – I was 391 kg/m³ in 2014.

Moisture:

The lowest moisture content of the three years study period i.e. 2012-2014 was 6.4% (2014) at station – I and highest was 43.4% (2013) at station – III. The minimum mean of density was observed at station – I and maximum was at station – III during the period of study. The lowest and highest moisture content in the study period in the respective years was 8.7% and 40.2% in 2012; 7.1% and 43.4% in 2013; and 6.4% and 43.28% in 2014.

Ash:

The ash content at various dumpsites during the study period was recorded with a lowest of 41.5% in 2013 and a highest of 74.2% in 2013. The lowest ash content was recorded at station – V and highest was at station – I in the year i.e. 2013. The minimum and maximum ash contents in the year 2013, 2013 and 2014 were 44.03% and 70.71%, 41.5% and 74.2%; and 44.67% and 71.7%, respectively. The lowest mean of ash in the entire study period was 43.4% at station – V and highest was 72.7% at station – I.

pH:

The lowest mean of pH in the three years' study period i.e.2012-2014 was 6.63 at station – I and highest mean was 7.45 at station – II. The minimum pH value was observed at station – I with 6.51 and maximum value was at station –II with 7.54. The lowest and highest pH values of 2012 were recorded at station – I and station – II respectively. The minimum and maximum pH of 2013 was 6.68 at station – IV and 7.53 at station – II. In the year 2014, station – I shown least pH value and station – II was with high pH value.

Nitrogen:

The Nitrogen content at various stations during the study period i.e. 2012-2014 was recorded with a lowest value of 0.49% and a highest of 1.13%. The mean of station – I during the study period was 0.66% (lowest) and mean of station – V was 0.9% (highest) recorded between the years 2012-2014. At station – I, the minimum Nitrogen content was recorded in 2014 and maximum was in 2013. At various stations like station – II, III, IV and V, the minimum and maximum values were 0.66% and 0.78%; 0.64% and 0.85%; 0.68 and 1.13% and 0.77 and 0.89 respectively.

Phosphate:

The lowest mean of Phosphate was recorded at station – IV (3.66%) and highest was at station – I (5.6%). The minimum Phosphate content of the study period was 3.2% and maximum was 6.9% during the year 2012-2014. The lowest Phosphate was observed at station – II (3.7%) and highest was 6.9% at station – I in 2012, similarly 3.2% and 5.3% in 2013; 3.9% and 4.73% in 2014.

Potash:

The lowest Potash content was recorded from station – IV in 2012 and highest was from station – I in the same year during the three years of study period i.e.2012-2014. The minimum mean of Potash was 4.7% at station – V and maximum mean was 16.2% at station – I during the period of study.

Total Organic Matter:

The Total Organic Matter recorded in the range of 9.5% and 38.51% during the period of study i.e. 2012-2014 from all stations of Greater Hyderabad. The lowest Total Organic Matter was observed at station – I and highest was at station – IV during the three years of study period. The minimum mean of Total Organic Matter in the entire study period was 11.38% from station – I and maximum was 37.41% from station – IV.

Total Organic Carbon:

The Total Organic Carbon content was observed at different stations in different percentages during the period of 2012-2014. The lowest Total Organic Carbon was observed at station – I in 2012 (9.75%) and highest was at station –IV in 2014 (21.48%) in the three years of study period. The minimum mean of Total Organic Carbon in all stations in the study period was 6.74% and maximum mean was 19.78%.

C/N Ratio:

The minimum C/N Ratio was recorded at station – I in 2014 (6.21) and maximum was recorded at station – II in 2014 (55.74). The lowest mean of C/N Ration was 7.92 and highest was 53.18 during the three years of study period i.e. 2012-2014. In the year wise minimum and maximum C/N Ratio's at all stations were 8.76 % 55.03 in 2012; 8.79 and 49.60in 2013; and 6.21 and 55.74 in 2014, respectively.

In the survey it was observed that 15% of the families had been staying at a close distance of <50 meters from the dumping site. Only 55% of the respondents were staying at distance between 50 - 100 meters from the dumping site; 25% were staying at distance between 100 - 200 meters; 5% were staying at distance more than 200 meters. Majority (60%) of the respondents have been staying at their present residences for 5-10 years; 15% for 1- 5 years; 14% for 10 - 15 years; 6% for above 15 years and 5% for less than 1 year.

Fires at the dump site are natural process. The residents (95%) often noticed smoke and fire in the dumping site. The respondents have cited the presence of stray animals and birds at the main dumping site. The stray animals included dogs, cows, buffaloes and cats, scavenging birds, such as eagle, cranes, etc. The residents depended on municipal tankers for drinking water (78%) and for other domestic uses people depended on public taps (55%) and common well (45%). All the respondents were unanimous in saying that Jawahar Nagar dumping site emitted foul smell. About 80% of the respondents stated that foul smell was mostly in the forenoon.

The people of the area suffer from diseases like Cholera (25%), Jaundice (20%), Diarrhea (25%); Dysentery (10%), Typhoid (15%) and other Diseases (5%). Majority of the households (55%) had different kinds of respiratory problems. Among these, 25% had Cough; 20% had Bronchitis; 15% sneezing; 20% Asthma; 10% Suffocation and 10% other diseases. In the survey it was found that 55% of the people are suffering with respiratory and 45% answered that they not suffering from the respiratory diseases.

People always generate solid waste through their daily activities, this solid waste need to be properly managed in a way to minimize the risk to the environment and human health. Therefore, a survey was conducted to understand the present status of domestic solid waste management in Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation. The analysis of the responses of households revealed that every day waste is generated in any house and this whole waste had to be temporarily stored before it is disposed in the next morning. Three fourths (73%) of the respondents revealed that they store the waste in a plastic bucket / dust bin and 25% of the households store in a plastic carry bag and only 2% throw out on road side. Now a days, most of the cities following segregation of waste. In the present study DSNR and Kukatpally residents have not shown any interest in the segregation of waste as wet and dry

waste. In the physical observation, it was found that 88% of the people did not segregate the waste, because they do not have the knowledge of segregation, only 12% of the people segregated the waste at source itself.

Waste disposal is very important in solid waste management. Various methods were adopted for the disposal of garbage by the households of DSNR and Kukatpally. About 75% of the households handed over the garbage to the waste collector, 25% of the households disposed the garbage in the municipal bins and 5% discarded on the road side. Discarded waste on the roads attract flies or vectors, contain materials that are dangerous to man and other living organisms. 92% of the households have agreed that the disposal of garbage is a serious problem. 96% of the households did not like to practice vermicomposting technology due to the lack of know-how and scientific awareness while the rest of the 4% households liked to practice the technology, if training is given.

With regard to disposal of metal, Glass and Plastic are recyclable wastes. In the present study it was clear that majority of the respondents (52%) disposed metal, glass and plastic articles into the storage bins along with the garbage; 38% of the households, selling to the rag pickers; 7% of the households, sold these wastes in local shops and 3% dumped it either at road side or the home premises. In the present study, we observed that 45% of households used < 20 plastic bags, 35% of the people used 20 – 50 bags, 15% used 50 – 75 bags and only 5% used more than 75 plastic bags per week and it was found that 65% of the households deposited their waste in the municipal waste bins, 20% of the households gave it free to the maid who sold it later, 5% sold at the local shops, 4% sold to the rag pickers, 3% carelessly thrown away and 3% burnt in their own premises. 92% of respondents liked to use other substitutes from plastic bags. Majority (88%) of the households in the survey preferred cloth bags, 10% preferred jute bags and 2% preferred paper bags, though the paper bags are eco - friendly material.

Rag pickers also called as waste collectors. These rag pickers visit the houses for waste collection of waste. Later they will segregate the recyclable materials from the waste. Households are paying the money to rag pickers for their services. In the present survey majority of households (85%) replied that rag pickers made visits to their houses for waste collection; 8% responded that rag pickers not visiting their houses or locality and 7% responded that they do know anything about rag pickers.

Municipal solid waste management is a very complex and challenging task for the collection, segregation, transport, disposal etc. As a part of questionnaire we asked the householders about the satisfaction of existing solid waste management practices in GHMC. Major percentages (65%) of the respondents were dissatisfied with the present solid waste management system of GHMC, whereas 35% reported satisfaction. 92% of the households believed that door to door it was a better method of waste collection because there is a chance of throw the waste outside or in open places and in directly we are generating the employment to the rag pickers.

Rag pickers collect the waste from houses, shops, markets, hospitals, commercial establishments and industries. Collection of waste is an important step in the solid waste management. In the investigation it was found that 42% of the rag pickers are collected the waste from residential areas; 30% collected from Market and commercial areas; 15% of them collected from hospitals; 10% of rag pickers collected from railway stations and 3% of rag pickers collected the waste from offices and educational institutions. Spending time by rag pickers on waste collection depends on the quantity of waste generated. In the study it was found that majority (65%) of the rag pickers spent 5-8 hrs in a day for the collection of waste; Rag pickers used different types of vehicles to collect the waste. It is revealed that 57% of rag pickers were not using any vehicle for waste collection; 20% using tri cycle; 15% using bicycle and 8% using motor cycle. A rag picker began his work as early as 4 AM. Whenever the bag was full, they returned to the store or trade center to sell these collections.

Many rag pickers preferred to collect the waste on all days except Sundays and holidays. 87% of the rag pickers roamed for collection on all days excluding Sunday's and holidays. Usually, the quantity of waste collected in a day depends on the number of hours spent for collection and number of houses covered. It was observed in the present study that only 3% collected more than 75 kg / day, 5% collected waste between 50 - 75 kg; 20% collected waste between 25 - 50 kg and 72% collected waste below 25 kg / day.

After segregation the recyclable materials from the waste, most of the rag pickers have the habit of selling the waste. In the investigation it was observed that 80% of waste collectors sold the collected waste materials on the same day itself. Rag pickers sold the waste on the payment basis. Few rag pickers received the money on same day, few of them at the weekend, few at the month end etc. In the study we noted that 25% of the rag pickers received the cost of waste collected on the same day itself. However, 40% received money at the weekend and 10% received money at the end of the month and 25% of them received the money based on the quality / quantity of collection. On collection and selling the waste, rag pickers are earning money. Majority 75% of the waste collectors earned Rs. 1000 - 1500 per month, 12% of the respondents earned Rs. 500 -1000, 10% earned a monthly income ranging more than 1500; 8% of them earned Rs. 200 - 500 per month.

The survey showed that 90% of waste collectors did not adopt any precautionary measures, 2% used antiseptic lotions, 8% used hand gloves; one percent used both gloves and antiseptic lotion. Lack of precautionary measures might produce health hazards to them. It was noticed that in the present study that 82% had wounds or injuries; 6% had body pains; 5% had skin or lung diseases and 7% said that they were not faced any health problems. In the present study, it was clear that 60% have been working for 3 years in this field. The Hyderabad city with its population reaching 10 million, generates 4000 tons of waste per day. A little above 45% of the MSW is biodegradable, which is left unused. The whole waste where ever it is generated in the city had to be transported to Jawahar Nagar dump site which is considered as for final disposal. The effects for composting are not adequate.

There is a huge potential of generating wealth from waste. A forward step in this direction requires:

- a) Separation of biodegradable and non-degradable wastes.

- b) Composting process be initiated with private partnership. it will be easier if GHMC takes initiate to involve some of the 900 people (rag pickers) living at the dump site. A 'subsistence model' can be worked out with no additional investment. A few people can be picked and trained in vermicomposting that provides livelihood to them with the buyback facility of the generated compost.

This not only provides livelihood top the poor but also saves a considerable amount of budget for urban horticulture. Another advantage of composting is a proper handling of organic waste will reduce the menace of mosquitoes and flies which are responsible for communicable and seasonal disease out breaks. The public perceptions on waste management also reflected the failure of GHMC to control odour, mosquitoes etc, at the dumpsite. Despite the public cooperation on door-to-door collection the GHMC was unable to continue waste handling stabilization. The entrepreneurs with high machineries come forward but could not continue long time because un scientific dumping and sorting of waste under these circumstance a 'Subsistence model' involving people who are living as 'dependents on dump' will give fruitful results.

- c) The non-biodegradable matter should be incinerated in order to reduce its volume. Open burning is currently practiced and should be dispersed with immediate effect. Recyclable from the dumpsite were collected by many rag pickers and nearly 600-700 rag pickers were getting Rs. 1500 per month. On an average the rough figures the amount crosses one crore rupees per year. These estimated were most primitive. If this is done in organized way by identifying genuine recyclers and the rag pickers selling these wastes to the identified recyclers will enhance this amount and will definitely reduce the menace of public health and provide assured livelihood to rag pickers. The dumpsites at Hyderabad if managed on a comprehensive basis will generate lot of revenue by which some percentage of expenditure on waste handling could be recovered.
- d) The major contributors of methane gas in India are the municipal solid waste dump sites. The nitrates/nitrites in the solid waste also are responsible for emission of Greenhouse gases. Nearly 4000 tonnes of waste generation is not a small thing to be ignores. If scientifically calculated the emissions of GHGs from Hyderabad dumpsites will have a significant contribution at national level.
- e) Landfill emissions can be reduced by only by sanitary landfills and not by open sumps.
- f) Hyderabad has been facing acute shortage of water resource for drinking, domestic and industrial purposes. The deterioration of quality with leachates entering the ground water further worsens the problem.

The public are prepared to cooperate with the GHMC in many areas and it is the responsibility of Municipal Corporation to realize and come forward with novel proposals of handling the municipal solid waste. The principles of energy from waste, wealth from waste, reuse/recycle/reduce the waste will certainly give positive results with high magnitude of solid wastes in Hyderabad.

References:

1. Benitez, S.O., Vega, M.Y. and Montenegro, M. 2008. Household solid waste characterization by family socioeconomic profile as unit of analysis. Resources, Conservation and Recycling. 52 (7): 992-999.
2. Bhide, A.D., and Shekdar, A.V., 1998. Solid waste management in Indian urban centers. International Solid Waste Association Times (ISWA) (1): 26-28.
3. Devi, K.S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V. and Dr. Niloufer S., 2016. Municipal Solid Waste Management in India – An Overview. **Asia Pacific Journal of Research**. 1(XXXIX):118-126.
4. Devi, K.S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S and Dr. Niloufer S., 2015. A Survey on Awareness of the People on Solid Waste Management at Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation, Telangana, India. **Global Journal of Research Analysis**. 3(10):117-121.
5. Devi, K.S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S, and Dr. Krishna, R.H., 2013. The Potential Adverse Health Effects of Residents Near Hazardous Municipal Solid Waste Dump Site- At Jawahar Nagar – Hyderabad. **Global Journal of Applied Environmental Sciences**.3(2):67-80.
6. Devi, K.S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S, and Dr. Krishna, R.H., 2014. Studies on the Solid Waste Collection by Rag Pickers at Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation, India. **International Research Journal Of Environment Sciences**. 3(1):1-10.
7. Kumar, S., Bhattacharyya, J.K., Vaidya, A.N., Chakrabarti, T., Devotta, S. and Akolkar, A.B. 2009. Assessment of the status of municipal solid waste management in metro cities, state capitals, class I cities, and class II towns in India: An insight, Waste Management 29: 883-895.
8. Ministry of Environment and Forest, MOEF, 2016. The Gazette of India. Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, New Delhi, India.
9. Ministry of Environment and Forests, MoEF, 2000. The Gazette of India. Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, New Delhi, India.
10. NEERI Report. 1996. Strategy paper on solid waste management in India. 1-7.
11. NEERI Report, Assessment of status of municipal solid waste management in metro cities, state capitals, Class I Cities and Class II Towns, 2005, 2010 and 2000.

12. Niloufer, S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S and Devi, K.S., 2014. Seasonal Variations in the Leachate Characteristics in MSW sites. **Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary**. 2(8): 479-487.
13. Niloufer, S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S., and Devi, K.S., 2013. Ground Water Quality in the Vicinity of Municipal Solid Waste dumpsites in Vijayawada, A.P. **International Journal of Engineering and Science Research**. 3(8): 419-425.
14. Niloufer, S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S., and Devi, K.S., 2013. Impact of Municipal Solid Waste on the Ground Water Quality in Vijayawada City, Andhra Pradesh. **Indian Journal of Applied Research**. 3(4): 62-64.
15. Niloufer, S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S., and Devi, K.S., 2013. Waste collection by Rag Pickers in the cities - A brief report. PARIPEX: **Indian Journal of Research**. 2(4): 211-214.
16. Niloufer, S., Dr. Swamy, A.V.V.S., and Devi, K.S., 2014. Gaseous emissions from MSW dumpsites in Vijayawada. **American International Journal of Research in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics**. ISSN- 2328-3491; 6(1): 67-73.
17. Pappu, A., Saxena, M., and Asokar, S.R., 2007. Solid Waste Generation in India and Their Recycling Potential in Building Materials. *Journal of Building and Environment*, 42 (6): 2311–2324.
18. Rajput, R., Prasad, G. and Chopra, A.K. 2009. Scenario of solid waste management in present Indian context. *J. Env. Sci*. 7 (1): 45-53.
19. Sharholy, M., Ahmad, K., Vaishya, R., and Gupta, R., 2007. Municipal solid waste characteristics and management in Allahabad, India. *Waste Management*, 27 (4), 490–496.
20. Shekdar, A.V., 1999. Municipal solid waste management – the Indian perspective. *Journal of Indian Association for Environmental Management*, 26 (2), 100–108.